

Evaluation Report

Evaluation of a new model of early intervention
and management of people with persistent pain

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Who We Are

In 2021 the Tritech Institute was launched. We are a team based in a bespoke facility within the Hywel Dda University Health Board comprising of industry-leading engineers, scientists and clinicians.

Our Institute

Here at TriTech Institute, we support the development of healthcare solutions on a local, national, and global level offering designers and manufacturers a single point of access to the NHS through a collaborative and agile approach.

What We Offer

The team's advanced skills in clinical and research design are combined with technical engineering expertise to manage the whole innovative pathway from early unmet need, through to concept design, prototyping, clinical testing, and real-world service evaluations.

Our Services

We provide specific services and solutions for *clinical engineering, research and innovation* and *value-based healthcare* and can also support with grant writing and submission.

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Situation

Clinical Background

Persistent pain can affect anyone of any age, at any time and is a significant health problem for a substantial proportion of the population. It is estimated that between 11% and 20% of adults are affected, with symptoms ranging from mild discomfort to debilitating pain.[1] Living with persistent pain has a negative effect on quality of life, not only physically, but also psychologically, socially and economically.[2] It can limit potential wellbeing, lower self-esteem, increase co-morbidities due to inactivity, have adverse effects on relationships and work, and be associated with feelings of shame and guilt.

Service Background and Context

Primary Care Pain Service: To address this Hywel Dda University Health Board (HDdUHB) have commissioned a pilot Primary Care Pain Service (PCPS) situated in a GP Cluster in North Ceredigion in West Wales, UK. The purpose of the PCPS is to provide a pathway to support early intervention using a bio-psychosocial (combined biological, psychological, and social) model of pain management.[3]

The pilot of the PCPS was set to run between June 2021 and June 2023 with the aim of providing several benefits to patients suffering persistent pain and reduce the overall burden at HDdUHB. Following initial successful indications a second PCPS was opened up in South Ceredigion in late 2022 (this site did not take part in this evaluation). The GP cluster covered by the pilot PCPS in North Ceredigion includes 7 GP practices which serve an estimated population of 47,000. Referral to the pilot service is open to three care pathways and is intended to treat people living with Osteoarthritis (OA), Fibromyalgia (FM) and unspecified persistent pain conditions (UPPC), whose pain condition is beginning to impact on their function, quality of life and mood. All patients under review at their GP practices who are found to be eligible for use of the PCPS will be offered the service. The service involves providing patients with material and education to help them better manage their pain as well as monitoring their quality of life and wellbeing. The service also provides access to a qualified psychologist and enrolment into a pain management program group that is held over 10 sessions.

Digital Aid: As part of the PCPS the chronic pain team will also be using a digital aid (Patient Knows Best PKB) aimed at allowing the team to disseminate educational material and PROMs to the patients. All patients who enter the service will be offered a PKB account, but it will not be a mandatory element of the PCPS, so that patients are not excluded. The PKB platform will host a library of resources and specific care plan to support their patient cohort, tailored by their clinical team to their needs as described above.

Service Aims

- People receiving the care they require in a timely fashion
- Seamless working across services and sectors
- More effective and efficient use of clinical resources
- Waiting times to reduce across pain services
- Increase expertise and management of pain in Primary Care

- Reduce prescribing rates for pain medications

Service Objectives

Aims to deliver a Bio-psychosocial approach to pain: self-management to enable a good quality of life. It addresses:

- Bio (physiological pathology)
- Psycho (thoughts emotions and behaviours)
- Social (socio-economical, socio-environmental, and cultural factors)

The Population

Around 600 patients are invited annually. Approximately 50% of the patients invited either decline or do not turn up. The possible reasons include:

- (i) the rural setting
- (ii) physical and mental health co-morbidities;
- (iii) preference for Welsh language intervention;
- (iv) time and length of sessions are not convenient.

Rationale and Aim of the Evaluation

The purpose of this piece of work is to carry out a service evaluation using mixed methods approach on the pilot PCPS to assess its effectiveness. In addition, this project will include an evaluation of the usefulness of a digital held record, such as PKB, as a way of facilitating dissemination of information/educational materials and in helping the healthcare practitioners monitor people using the service.

Evaluation Plan

A mixed-methods approach was utilised to meet the aim of the evaluation via the objectives and outcomes set out below.

The aim of the work outlined in this document is to provide a service evaluation of the PCPS that is being piloted by HDDUHB. This service evaluation will be divided into two main objectives:

Objective 1: Service Evaluation of the Primary Care Pain Service

To evaluate the effectiveness of the PCPS. The service evaluation will focus on pilot's early intervention impact on quality of life (QoL), wellbeing and outcomes for patients living with OA, FM and UPPC.

Objective 2: Service Evaluation of the PKB Platform use in the Pain Service

To evaluate the utility of the PKB platform this service evaluation will assess why patients decided to use the platform. The evaluation will also assess what PKB resources patients found most beneficial and whether patients found the extra functionality allowed by the PKB system (upload data they generate (experiences, results, medication etc) and help in organising/managing their care) was useful. The evaluation of PKB will aim to also consider the Health Care Professional's (HCP) perspectives.

Measures

Three care pathways will be available for assignment purposes to the new pain service – OA, FM and (UPPC) and all patients diagnosed and eligible will be offered the service. Once confirmed as eligible patients will be initially contacted by first contact practitioners and the cluster-based psychologist. General Practitioners can also raise awareness of the primary care pain service if appropriate. As part of the referral to the PCPS it must first be identified that it is suitable and appropriate to treat the potential patient using a bio-psychosocial model of pain management. This is done as part of their standard care and is carried out by their care team with the correct training and expertise. A PKB account will be offered to all patients eligible for the PCPS. Patients will be provided a unique log in and then be asked if they wish to use the PKB platform as a way for them to access their library of resources, a care plan and specific support information. Patients will be advised that the usefulness of PKB is being evaluated alongside their routine care and that they will be invited to give feedback once they have been using it for at least three months. For those patients unable or unwilling to use the PKB system the resources will be provided in a paper format, they will be asked if they would like to provide a reason why they do not wish to use the PKB platform.

Study Type

Service Evaluation

Study Design: Service evaluation

The service evaluation will attempt to explore the two main objectives of this project: to evaluate the PCPS and the utility of PKB. The service evaluation will use a mixed methodology and draw on several different data sources. The evaluation of the service will involve comparison of pre/post intervention PROM's, tracking data and health resource utilization statistics recorded by PKB. Each person who takes part in the PCPS will be provided with a pre assessment of their quality of life and wellbeing which will be reassessed after 3 months (post intervention) to evaluate if the PCPS has had an impact on the person's life. The use of PROMS (Appendix 1) at baseline and 3 months is already a part of the patient's standard care pathway on the PCPS.

A sample of patients and healthcare workers will also be invited to take part in semi structured interviews to gain perspectives on the PCPS and PKB. A final report will be completed using the data collected.

Eligibility Criteria and Subject Selection

As this is a service evaluation there is no specific eligibility requirement. All patients who are found eligible and use the PCPS over the 6-month recruitment period of the evaluation will be entered into the service evaluation. Eligibility to the PCPS includes being diagnosed and currently on the care pathway for either OA, FM and UPPC and being suitable for treatment with a bio-psychosocial (combined biological, psychological, and social) model of pain management as determined by clinical professionals. For the patient interview process, this will be offered on a first come first served basis. All participants in the pain service will be offered a chance for an interview to discuss the PCPS and the PKB.

Service Evaluation Duration and Timescales

The plan is to carry out a service evaluation over a 12-month period. Baseline data will be collected over the year 2022. The start date was Jan 2022, the project will run for 12 months.

Power Calculation

As this is a service evaluation no formal power calculation has been performed. Data collected between June 2021 to October 2021 has shown that between 60-70 patients have been entered into the PCPS so far. Therefore, it is projected that over the course of referral into the PCPS in 2022 we expect around 60-120 patients are likely to be entered into the evaluation.

Data Sources

Data collected to complete the service evaluation will include:

- **PCPS: Patient Recruitment, Demographics and Service Usage Information:** As part of the patient's standard care pathway we will collect data on the patients recruited into the study and how they used the PCPS.
- **PROMS: Pre and Post intervention assessments:** As part of the patient's standard care pathway in the PCPS a PROM assessment is carried out pre and post intervention (after 3 months) using the GAD PHQ Pain Self-efficacy and Early Intervention Persistent Pain in Primary Care (see Appendix 2). The PROM assessment is handled by the standard care team. In the service evaluation dissemination of these PROM's will be handled in either a digital (PKB) or paper format. These PROM's will capture data on patient's mood, function, and self-efficacy.
- **PKB: usage/tracking data:** Information will also be collected from aggregated PKB administrative data on usage of the different resources. This data will be collected in a non-identifiable form and analysed. For patients that refuse the offer of PKB the reasons why will be recorded as they may be an important aspect in evaluating the use of digital aids in the service. We will also evaluate PKB compliance and usability. In addition, at the 3 month post intervention mark patients will also be asked to fill out a questionnaire based around their views on using the PKB platform (see Appendix 3)
- **Patient interviews:** A small number (n=10-20) of patients using the service will be invited to take part in a semi structured interview. The interview will provide feedback on how effective they thought the new service was in helping them to understand and self-manage their pain. For patients using the PKB platform these interviews will also explore their views on its effectiveness. Interviews to be conducted by telephone or video-conference. A topic guide can be found in Appendix 4.
- **Healthcare professionals interviews:** In addition health care professionals (n=5) involved in the new primary care pain service will be asked to take part in semi-structured interviews to capture their experiences of the service and PKB. Interviews to be conducted by telephone or video-conference. The people who will be interviewed will include specialist

psychologist managing the new service in the GP cluster, physiotherapist, GPs referring to the services, and a practice pharmacist.

Generate empirical data using mixed methodological approaches (questionnaires/Surveys & interview).

- Development of learning and teaching materials of ILA Innovation and Transformation.
- Development of a final report including background, methodology, research outcomes.
- Dissemination of outcomes and final report will be provided to all partners in the project
- VBHC case study development.
- Strengthening Industry-UHB-Academic collaboration(s).
- Intelligence on end-user perception of digital PKB.
- Knowledge on technology acceptance and adoption from clinician and patient's perspective. The novel application of a mixed methodological approach to understanding the interaction between chronic pain patients and innovative pain management intervention.
- An understanding of the dynamics surrounding acceptance and adoption of the PCPS from the patient's perspective which influence the behavioural intention of patients to use of the new intervention.
- Ease of access to quality pain management intervention.
- Acceptability, accessibility, functionality and efficacy of the intervention
- Opportunities to implement as part of routine care at the Chronic Pain Service
- Gauge the scalability of the platform across a wider patient population and push for its adoption into other health boards.

Findings

PCPS Patient Recruitment, Demographics and Service Usage Information

During the period from Jan 2022 to Dec 2022, we had a total of 149 were found to be appropriate for the primary care pain management service. Of the 149 patients referred into the service in 2022 only 124 were found to be eligible with the remaining 25 being referred onto other services. Figure 1 also shows that referrals into the service over the year 2022, was not constant with 26 patients being refereed in one month and as few as 4 in another. Table 1 shows the sources of where referrals into the service originate, with the biggest referrers being GP and Clinical Psychologist who account for over 70% of all referrals. Of the patients seen at the clinic 78% (116) presented with persistent pain, 14% (21) presented with Fibromyalgia and 8% (12) presented with Osteoarthritis. Of all the patients recruited 76% were female (113) and 24% (36) were male. This distribution of age for both male and female can be seen in Figure 2, showing an even spread amongst the age groups with people between the ages of 45-64 being the most common for both males and females.

Figure 1: Chart showing the referrals into the service throughout the year of 2022

Table 1	% referrals
Acute Physician	1%
ANP	4%
Assistant Psychologist	1%
GP	42%
Health Care Assistant	2%
Physician Associate	1%
Pharmacist	1%
Physio	14%
Practice nurse	2%
Clinical Psychologist	30%
Self	1%

Table 1: Table displaying where the patient referrals into the PCPS originated

Figure 2: Chart showing age distribution for both males and females

To date of all the patients who have completed the PCPS we saw a significant difference in the number of sessions that people needed before they could be discharged. The median number of sessions needed by people using the service was 6 (see figure 3).

Figure 3: Graph show the number of sessions required in the PCPS before a patient was fit to be discharged.

PROMS: Pre and Post intervention assessments:

Following being referred into the service, at the beginning of the service patients are provided a copy of the PROM for them to completed to gather a baseline understanding of the patients condition. The prom is provided either in a paper form or through the PKB platform depending on patient choice. Of the 124 patients accepted into the service 94 opted for a paper copy of the PROM and 30 opted for the PROM to be completed through the PKB system. Of the 94 that opted for a paper copy only 7 patients opted to return their PROMs (7.4%), these patients were asked on their initial consultation and were followed up by phone and asked again at their first session visit. Despite this patient still showed poor compliance with filling out PROM data. Of the 30 people who asked to complete the PROM using PKB, 14 filled out their PROMs (46.7%). Of the 21 patients who did complete their baseline PROM only 1 patient complied with completing the post intervention PROM. Patients were asked when they were discharged from the service to fill out the post PROM and were also followed up, but still the PROMs were not completed. Despite the best efforts of the healthcare teams and the PCPS team, there was limited formal response to PROMS completion, further requests were sent multiple times and both email and paper format were offered.

The results of the PROM scores can be seen in Table 2. Three main PROMS were used (see Appendix 1). The first number is Pain Self Efficacy Questionnaire – total out of 60 where a higher score indicating a person’s higher level of confidence in coping with their pain. The Mean self-efficacy score was 24.8 (SD 11.5) indicating a poor level of self-efficacy in these patients. The second PROM is PHQ- 9 depression score -the PHQ-9 indicates a person’s level of depression from: 0-4 none, 5-9 mild, 10-14 moderate, 15-19 moderately severe, 20-27 severe. The mean PHQ-9 score was 14.0 (SD 6.1) indicating moderately to moderately severe level of depression in this group of patients. With 5 (out of 21) of the patients reporting severe depression. The third PROM used is the GAD-7 which provides an Anxiety score where values of 5, 10, and 15 are taken as the cut-off points for mild, moderate and severe anxiety, respectively. Where the mean score was 11.3 (SD 7.1) indicating a moderate

level of anxiety in these patients with a significant number of the patients displaying severe anxiety (7 out of 21).

Baseline Self efficacy	POST Self efficacy	Baseline PHQ-9	POST PHQ-9	Baseline GAD-7	POST GAD-7
23		14		10	
17		17		19	
35		13		13	
37		7		3	
21		13		5	
35		5		7	
11		12		14	
43		15		15	
45		1		0	
21		-		-	
15		20		23	
6		25		18	
21	20	21	18	21	17
12		21		16	
18		8		0	
20		21		21	
24		13		8	
31		18		11	
39		8		7	
10		14		11	
36		13		3	

Table 2: Table showing the results of the PROMs for patients who complied and completed the PROMs

PKB: usage/tracking data:

All patients who were referred into the PCPS and were eligible for the service were offered a PKB registration account. Of the 124 patients offered the PKB account only 30 people chose to register an account, this shows an uptake of around 25%. A further 20 accounts were created for patients, but the patients did not follow through with the registration (see figure 4). Figure 4 also shows the dates when people registered for their PKB, the graph shows a relatively consistent registration throughout the year. Figure 5 shows the age and gender of the people who registered for a PKB account with the majority being female (27 out of 30) and the median age being between 45-54 years old.

Figure 6 shows the usage data and how registered patients used the PKB system. The figures indicate that despite there being 30 registered users there were never more than 5 people using the system in any one month. This indicates that despite registering most patients did not use the PKB system more than a handful of times. Figure 7 shows how often the users were interacting with the PKB platform and what for. It shows that the vast majority of patients used the system to message their healthcare professionals or to complete paper work (PROMs and PREMs) or access information about the pain service. The PKB system also

shows the number of reminders sent to patients to complete the PROMs (36 reminder requests were sent) and when the PROMs were completed (14).

Figure 4: Figure showing total number of registrations and when the registrations took place.

Figure 5: Age and Gender of patients who registered for a PKB account.

Monthly active users timeline

Figure 6: Graph showing the number of patients who accessed the PKB system per month

Figure 7: Graph and table showing the total number of times the PKB system was used and what it was used for by patients.

Figure 8: Graph showing the requests sent to patient who have registered to complete the PROM and the number of completed PROMs.

Patient questionnaires and interviews:

Patients were engaged throughout the service to gather perspectives of both:

- Effectiveness and acceptability of the PCPS being offered
- Effectiveness and useability of the PKB as a digital aid to the PCPS

Patient questionnaire: PCPS

The patient questionnaire for the PCPS can be seen in Appendix 2a. All patients who were discharged from the service were asked to complete the questionnaire. No formal responses were returned at this stage (as they were handed out with the post PROMs), telephone follow ups were conducted with all the patients and in total we received 17 responses to the PCPS questionnaire, following the phone call, the responses to the questions can be seen in Figure 9. The results from the questionnaire are overwhelmingly positive. With no negative results being in any of the questions being recorded. It shows a high level of satisfaction with the PCPS and a perceived reduction in tension and anxiety with a improved mood following completion of the PCPS programme.

Figure 9: Graphs showing the responses to the patient survey on the effectiveness and acceptability of the PCPS

Figure 10 further illustrates that the PCPS also provides patients with an increased understanding of their own pain and Provides effective techniques and strategies for patients to help them manage that pain.

Figure 10: Graphs showing the responses to the patient survey on the effectiveness and acceptability of the PCPS

Patient questionnaire: PKB

The patient questionnaire for PKB can be seen in Appendix 2b. All patients were asked to complete the questionnaire when they were discharged from the PCPS. No formal responses were returned at this stage (as they were handed out with the post PROMs), telephone follow ups were conducted with all the patients and in total we received 11 responses to the PKB questionnaire, following the phone call, the responses to the questions can be seen in Figure 11.

The results from the questionnaire on PKBs acceptability by people who have completed the PCPS shows that the platform did not seem to help them in managing their pain. They also stated that they did not think the platform was either easy to use or the information on the platform was engaging. Ultimately, they would not recommend the platform to other people starting the PCPS. The reasons for these issues was explored further in the patient interviews.

Figure 11: Graphs showing the responses to the patient survey on the effectiveness and acceptability of the PKB as a platform to support the PCPS

Patient interviews

The interview schedule for patients can be found in Appendix 3. 30 patients who had completed the PCPS (and had registered for the use of PKB) were approached for interview. Of those 30, 11 people agreed to be interviewed. The responses to the questions can be seen in appendix 4, the results of which are summarised below.

The overall opinion from the patients was that the PCPS has definitely helped them in a number of ways. Patients have expressed that they have found benefit in the learning materials, the information around exercise and the senses of community, being able to share their experiences with professionals and other people suffering with similar conditions. The key aspects being that patients expressed a greater understanding of their pain, an increased ability to manage their own pain and medication, an improvement in

mental health and increased confidence in their own abilities. Almost all patients interviewed would recommended the service to others, identifying excellent benefits, particular around learning how to pace themselves and not become over reliant on medication.

Two patients did identify that they did not get any benefit from the service themselves, either being too far along their pain journey or having taken part in similar programmes in the past. Both patients identified that the course was aimed more at people with the early signs of pain and that it would provide benefit to those patients. They identified that for anyone with no experience of PMPs the PCPS would be of benefit.

All patients were asked about the PKB platform, almost universally the participants agreed that they did not get much value from the PKB platform. One patient said 'I did use it, it wasn't much help'. Several patients also complained about the technology and its accessibility with one stating 'It wouldn't work, I would have liked to use it but I just couldn't logged onto it'. Overall, the impression of PKB was that it didn't really add to the patient experience, with many patients complaining that they didn't really understand what it was for and how they should use it. The underlying reasons seem to be that the patients either felt that did not understand the reason or usefulness of the PKB platform or that they just weren't engaged with it, enough.

In summary the key finding from the interviews was that the patients who have used the service gained benefit from it and that they were highly satisfied with what the service had to offer and would recommended it to others. The patients responses in the interviews identify that the service:

- Helped patients understand their pain
- Provided techniques to better manage their pain
- Reduced anxiety
- Improved confidence
- The use of a digital patient held record was not really found to be of benefit

Staff interviews

The interview schedule for staff can be found in Appendix 5. 4 members of staff were approached, Clinical psychologist, member of the pharmacy team, GP, and physiotherapist. The responses to the questions can be seen in appendix 5, the results of which are summarised below.

Results from the staff interviews identified that there were some issues during the initial set up of the service, but after the service was embedded into the cluster the service has preformed well. It was noted that the PCPS team have integrated themselves seamlessly into the service and have built working relationships with the other teams in the service providing a more well-rounded and inclusive experience for staff and patients. A key aspect has been the early access to support for the patients and that the service has provided benefit to some of the most difficult patients to manage in the cluster. The staff interviewed

did not identify and negative impact of the PCPS on the cluster and did identify that it has relieved some of the internal pressures within the cluster.

The overall feedback from patients that has come to the staff around the cluster is positive 'I know many of the patients that I spoke to have found it very helpful'. This has primarily been due to the service providing people with an avenue to discuss their problems and work through them, to be educated about their condition and to learn of strategies and techniques to manage their pain.

The key issues or barriers still identified within the service is that the PCPS team are heavily focused on managing the patients and delivery the pain management program to the patients. This has highlighted that the team lacks the capacity for some of the more administrative tasks such as PROM collection and management or the PKB (or digital health records).

Conclusions

The finding of this report shows that the PCPS has been successful in reaching 124 patients in the 2022 calendar year. This is at the top of the estimate of what could be expected in this primary care cluster. It has shown that the intervention or a early stage pain management programme to these patients has been successful, without the PCPS patients could have waiting up to over a year to have access to a secondary care provided Pain management program.

The key finding from this show the overall positive interaction with the PCPS from the patients and staff. The patient survey shows a significantly high positive responses particularly in the ability of the PCPS to improve patients undertraining of pain and providing the ability to patients to better manage their pain. The survey also identified high patient satisfaction with the service leading to a reduction in anxiety and improvement in mood. The key reasons for this can be seen in the responses to the interviews, where the availability of a healthcare professional or peers to talk through and work through issues has helped significantly. In addition, the training particularly around pacing and education around pain have proven to be particularly successful for patients. Staff around the cluster have also identified benefits, with positive patient feedback, plus the PCPS has helped to relieve some of the internal pressures within the cluster. The PCPS has provided an additional support in helping to manage some of the clusters most difficult to manage patients. The PCPS has in turn been highly recommended by both staff and patients.

One of the key barriers and failures of the service is that whilst patients are happy to engage with the PCPS and turn up for their sessions and interventions (see Figure 3), care teams have significant issues in getting patients to complete PROM data, particularly from this group of patients. The data does suggest that if patients can be engaged with a digital element or patient held record this may be improved, as seen by the significantly higher return of the baseline PROMs with people who registered for a PKB account. However, this did not translate to post intervention PROM collection as patients in turn struggled to stay engaged with the PKB platform. It was seen that after the first initial uses of the PKB patients either forgot about it or stopped using it completely.

In conclusion, the service has been well received by patients and staff across the cluster. The service provides benefit to the patients who engage with the service, and the service provides an additional support to many patients who would go unmanaged without it. Despite this there are some areas for improvement within the service particularly around the collection of PROM data and general administrative duties within the service.

Recommendations

Recommendation 1: PROM delivery: Administrative Support

The first recommendation to improve the service would be to build into the service an additional mechanism to improve PROM collection for the service. A key finding has been that the current system is not effective. The clinical staff delivering the interventions and managing the patients do not have the time or capacity for the constant chasing and collection of the PROMs or its analysis. Therefore, the main recommendation for the service would be the acquisition of administrative support for the service. The administrative support would provide the capacity to be a contact for patients and enable reminders and support around PROM collection within the service.

Recommendation 2: Digital held record

The second recommendation revolves around the use of the PKB or a patient held record. Whilst many people could see its potential this potential was not recognised in this report with patients not really understanding why the PKB account was there and as a result not utilising or using it. In addition, the staff running the service did not have the time or capacity within the service to train, educate and manage the PKB system as effectively as possible. A digital held record that can be used for delivering PROMs and educational material could be tried again, however, if tried again it would be recommended that additional administrative support is provided to the service to manage the PKB platform and the patients. If administrative support is not available this report would recommend that a digital held record is not utilised.

Recommendation 3: Wider Rollout of the Service

The Third recommendation from this evaluation would be a continued rollout and spread of the service to other primary care GP clusters. Our findings (whilst not supported by PROM collection) has received very positive reviews and comments from both staff and patients. With most patients claiming some benefit from the service. Staff have identified that the service is relieving pressure and support some of the most difficult to manage and help patients in the cluster. The recommendation would be to identify 1-2 new clusters and start to repeat the service at these locations taking on board the other recommendations in this project.

Appendix 1 PROMS

Early Intervention Persistent Pain in Primary Care

Name: _____ DOB: _____ Date: _____

Pain Self-Efficacy Questionnaire

Please rate how **confident** you are that you can do the following things at present, **despite the pain**. To indicate your answer circle **one** of the numbers on the scale under each item, where 0 = not at all confident and 6 = completely confident.

1. I can enjoy things despite the pain.

0	1	2	3	4	5	6
Not at all confident						Completely confident

2. I can do most of the household chores (eg. Washing up, tidying up etc) despite the pain.

0	1	2	3	4	5	6
Not at all confident						Completely confident

3. I can socialise with my friends and family members as often as I used to, despite the pain.

0	1	2	3	4	5	6
Not at all confident						Completely confident

4. I can cope with my pain in most situations.

0	1	2	3	4	5	6
Not at all confident						Completely confident

5. I can do some form of work despite the pain ("work" includes housework, paid and unpaid work).

0	1	2	3	4	5	6
Not at all confident						Completely confident

6. I can still do many of the things I enjoy doing, such as hobbies or leisure activities, despite the pain.

0	1	2	3	4	5	6
Not at all confident						Completely confident

7. I can cope with my pain without medication.

0	1	2	3	4	5	6
Not at all confident						Completely confident

8. I can still accomplish most my goals in life, despite the pain.

0	1	2	3	4	5	6
Not at all confident						Completely confident

9. I can live a normal lifestyle, despite the pain.

0	1	2	3	4	5	6
Not at all confident						Completely confident

10. I can gradually become more active, despite the pain.

0	1	2	3	4	5	6
Not at all confident						Completely confident

Patient-specific activity scoring scheme

Please identify up to five important activities you are unable to perform or are having difficulty with as a result of your problem eg putting socks on, shopping.

Using the 0-10 scale, please identify how difficult undertaking that task has been for you over the last week.

Activity	0 Unable to perform activity	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10 Able to perform activity at the same level as before injury or problem
1											
2											
3											
4											
5											

PHQ-9 & GAD-7

Over the last 2 weeks, how often have you been bothered by any of the following problems? <i>(Please circle your answer)</i>	Not at all	Several days	More than half the days	Nearly every day
Little interest or pleasure in doing things	0	1	2	3
Feeling down, depressed or hopeless	0	1	2	3
Trouble falling or staying asleep, or sleeping too much	0	1	2	3
Feeling tired or having very little energy	0	1	2	3
Poor appetite or overeating	0	1	2	3
Feeling bad about yourself – or that you are a failure, or have let yourself or your family down	0	1	2	3
Trouble concentrating on things, such as reading the newspaper or watching television	0	1	2	3
Moving or speaking so slowly that other people could have noticed? Or the opposite – being so fidgety or restless that you have been moving around a lot more than usual	0	1	2	3
Thoughts that you would have been better off dead or hurting yourself in some way	0	1	2	3

PHQ9 – Total score –

Over the last 2 weeks, how often have you been bothered by any of the following problems? <i>(Please circle your answer)</i>	Not at all	Several days	More than half the days	Nearly every day
Feeling nervous, anxious or on edge	0	1	2	3
Not being able to stop or control worrying	0	1	2	3
Worrying too much about different things	0	1	2	3
Trouble relaxing	0	1	2	3
Being so restless that it is hard to sit still	0	1	2	3
Becoming easily annoyed or irritable	0	1	2	3
Feeling afraid as if something awful might happen	0	1	2	3

GAD-7 – Total score -

Appendix 2a PCPS questionnaire

A mixed methods service evaluation of the GP cluster pain service and PKB

User Experience and Feedback

Read each statement carefully then indicate whether or not you agree with the statement

(1 = not at all helpful, 5 = very helpful)	1	2	3	4	5
How helpful did you find your assessment with the service					

(1 = Not at all satisfied 5 = Very satisfied)	1	2	3	4	5
How satisfied were you with the service?					

(1 = much worse 10 = much better)	1	2	3	4	5
Compared to before the PCPS do you feel your mood is?					

(1 = less anxious 5 = more anxious)	1	2	3	4	5
Compared to before the PCPS. How would you score your anxiety now?					

Appendix 2b PKB questionnaire

A mixed methods service evaluation of the GP cluster pain service and PKB

User Experience and Feedback

Read each statement carefully then indicate whether or not you agree with the statement

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree or Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
The PKB digital platform helped me better manage my pain					

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree or Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
The PKB digital platform was easy to use					

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree or Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
The content of the PKB digital platform was easy to understand					

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree or Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
The content of the PKB platform was engaging and interesting					

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree or Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I was able use PKB without any issues					

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree or Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
After completing the PKB and the PCPS I better understand my pain					

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree or Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
the PCPS has taught we techniques and strategies to help me manage my pain					

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree or Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
The PKB digital platform was too difficult to use					

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree or Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I would recommend the PKB digital platform to other people who have persistent pain					

Appendix 3 Patient Interview Topic Guide

Patient Questions

POST INTERVENTION INTERVIEWS

Semi Structured interview questions

- 1) Do you feel you are better able to manage your pain following completing the PCPS?
 - What do you think the reasons for this are?
 - What lessons has the PCPS taught you? (if any?)
 - Do you think you have a better understanding of what causes persistent pain?
 - Does this knowledge give you more confidence in being able to manage your own pain?
- 2) Was the PKB platform easy to use?
- 3) Overall what did you think of PKB platform?
- 4) Which specific parts of the PCPS did you find useful or helpful (If any)?
 - o Education?
 - o Exercises?
 - o Pain management techniques?
- 5) Were any specific parts of the PCPS unhelpful?
 - o Education?
 - o Exercises?
 - o Pain management techniques?
 - o Particular modules?
- 6) What improvements would you suggest for the PCPS and/or PKB?
- 7) Would you recommend the PCPS and or PKB to other people living with persistent pain?

Appendix 4 Patient Interview Topic Guide

Patient Answers

POST INTERVENTION INTERVIEWS

Semi Structured interview questions

1) **'Do you feel you are better able to manage your pain following the PCPS?'**

'yes definitely'

'at first I was unsure but after a while I really started to feel it was helping'

'No'

'Without a doubt'

'I didn't feel I was learning anything; we were going over stuff I had already done.'

Some points were helpful, but I had already done some of this before, I think it works for people, but just not for me'

'yes'

'definitely'

• **What do you think the reasons for this are?**

'because she taught me about pacing taught me how to slow down, taking your time, prioritizing'

'I have long term pain, it's quite debilitating i am far down the pain journey and already have my own coping mechanisms and the course didn't add to anything I already knew'

'it was nice to listen to other peoples experiences and know I wasn't alone'

'it taught me how to pace myself, I learnt a lot around what (clinical psychologist) told me and taught me'

'I had already done something similar years back'

'there were other people there who I could talk to at the group sessions'

'The opportunity to speak to someone about my pain'

'The time that was given and answered all my questions, very good listener'

• **Do you think you have a better understanding of what causes persistent pain?**

'Yes definitely'

'oh yes'

'without doubt'

'It showed me there were alternatives to my medication'

'No, I didn't learn anything new'

'Yes, it taught me I was relying on medication'

'not for me, but people new to this stuff would definitely benefit from the course'

'yes'

• **Does this knowledge give you more confidence in being able to manage your own pain?**

'I have way more confidence in myself now'

'yes I know I can do things now'

'yes, definitely'
'yes I have learned to believe in myself'
'the course has shown me my pain doesn't control me'
'No'
'Yes definitely, I found the one to one sessions to be better, I got more out of that'
'the knowledge from these types of courses definitely give you more confidence in managing your pain, this one didn't for me as I had already done something similar'
'yes'

2) Was the PKB platform easy to use?

'I thought it was pretty easy to use I just didn't use it'
'It was ok, I had some issues to start with'
'I didn't really use it much'
'not really'
'I found it difficult, but then again I didn't really use it much'
'I didn't use it'
'I didn't get it, im not very technical'
'I thought it was easy enough to log in and stuff, but I just didn't get what I was using it for, It was really explained to me'
'no, I think if someone had showed me how to use it then it might have been a different story, but as it was I just ended it up not using it.'
'It wouldn't work, I would have liked to use it but I just couldn't logged onto it'
'yes I did use it, it wasn't much help'

3) Overall what did you think of PKB platform?

'I didn't really get it, if I am honest, I didn't see what it was offering'
'I didn't use it'
'I forgot all about it to be honest'
'I couldn't really understand how it was supposed to help me'
'I didn't really feel like it was explained to me very well'
'I think if someone had explained why I was using it I might have used it more'
'I wasn't really supported with it, I logged in and didn't really understand what I was supposed to do next'
'it was never really explained to be what I was using it for'
'I didn't know what was expected of me, if I'm honest'
'I had a lot of computer issues so couldn't use it'
'Just not for me. Sceptical over its helpfulness'

4) Which specific parts of the PCPS did you find useful or helpful (If any)?

'All of it'
'I got something out of all of it'
'the interaction with people helped me the most'
'just being able to talk, helped the most'
'having someone who understood and cared was the best part for me'
'I think it's the education side of it, when you live with pain you forget things, it taught me to pace myself'
'Some of the exercises were ok, being able to work though some of my issues'

'I found it really helped with my Mental health'
'I had stopped going to the gym, going to the sessions talking to people, gave me the confidence to go back to the gym, and I wouldn't have done that otherwise'
'I have made some great friends'
'Being listened to '
'It gave me the tools to help manage my pain'
'Staff very professional understanding, knowledgeable and helpful'
'They (staff) really listened to and reassured me, encouraging me greatly'

5) Were any specific parts of the PCPS unhelpful?

'No it was all helpful'
'No'
'No not really'
'whilst it didn't really help me, I can definitely see how it could help new people'
'I think it was all pretty good'
'I cant think of anything'
'not off the top of my head no'
'not really'
'as I mentioned it didn't really help me as I had don't it before'
'No I think it all had its uses you need to find out what'

6) What improvements would you suggest for the PCPS?

'Nothing'
'No not really its really good I can really management pain better'
'I cant think of any'
'I think its works fine the way it is'
'I cant really comment as I have already said it didn't really learn anything new but other people might. Maybe a course designed for people with more established pain would be useful'
'More comfortable chairs at the meeting venue'

7) Would you recommend the PCPS to other people living with persistent pain?

'God yes everyone with the same stuff as me should try it'
'Without a doubt'
'Definitely'
'its had a massive impact on my life so yes I would definitely recommend it'
'yes'
'people new on their pain journey would probably get some benefit'
'Yes I would if I was in a bad situation again I would like to use the service again'
'Basically knowing it was there is reassuring knowing there was help there if I needed it.'
'Absolutely you don't know until you try it. I was always negative about this sort of thing in the past'
'The time and effort that went into the appointment was 10 out of ten felt that I was listened to'

Appendix 5 Staff Interview Topic Guide

Staff Questions & Answers

SERVICE INTERVIEWS

Semi Structured interview questions

Q1: So what was your overall view of how they implemented the service?

'the service has worked really well for us in us with surgery. They work one or two days a week with us. They see their patients, and then they can come and talk to me, and the rest of the team. So its been really good for patients. We kind of bounce ideas off each other.

'there were some early problems and it took longer than expected to set up, but once it got going it has worked well'

'I don't really have much interaction with the team, I just refer patients when I cant help them, or vice versa, that being said I think it has worked well'

'the service has been great and really helped'

'(they) have fitted in really well within our surgery'

'I think it has worked really well, I know it took abit to get it set up and started but now its been running for a while I think its great'

Q2: Did you think it has worked?

'that whole element of, you know, giving people, time, allowing people to talk about it, giving them that time to, you know, actually explain what they're experience is and then providing, that feedback for their experience.

'yes I definitely think it has been a success, I know many of the patients that I spoke to have found it very helpful'

'yes the team has fitted in well at the surgery and just got on with it, it has definitely benefitted some of our most difficult patient'

'I think so, it has added that extra level of care the patients would not have received otherwise'

'one of the biggest problems was the PROMs, I just didn't have the time or capacity to chase down the proms, my work was focussed on the patients and the Service.

Q3: Do you think there's any negative effects on the on the primary care?

'No, definitely not. No, it's been all positive for us really. You know, it has had some really good success with some of our most difficult patients.'

'cant really say'

'no, I wouldn't say so, they have fit into the surgery really well and become part of the team. They get on with it'

'I don't think so no'

Q4: Has there's been any impact on the staff?

'its definitely has taken work away from the rest of the clinical staff in the surgery'

'No definitely no negative effects'

'it's alleviated some of the pressures'

*'it hasn't had any impact on me but I cant comment on the rest of the surgery'
'its had an impact in a positive way by taking on a number of our patients and providing them with a service and attention we may not have been able to offer without them'
'I just didn't have the time to complete all the jobs particularly the PROM collection, 'I really would have valued some additional administrative support to help with this aspect.'*

Q5: any further comments?

*'only, we're really glad to have the service and we hoping really are hoping that it will continue then.'
'We really value the team and what they are doing.'
'no not really'*

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